

Investigating paleobiological rhythms: A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) approach to ichnofabric analysis

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Abstract. An analysis commonly used in studying depositional systems involves integrating lithofacies and ichnofossil data. It is important to note that organisms play a significant role in creating ichnofossils, being the primary agents responsible for their formation. This research examines the bioturbation index (BI), ichnodiversity (ID), number of behaviors (NB), penetration depth (PD), and ichnofossil diameter (DM) across 640 ichnofabric units in the 20 outcrops of Samarinda Area, Kutai Basin by using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The principal component analysis produced two main components, PC-1 and PC-2, with their respective scores. The scores are visually represented in oscillation curves incorporated into the sedimentary log, highlighting the cyclostratigraphy. The ichnofabric oscillation curves suggest the paleobiological rhythm, indicating the trace-making population's movement intensity and home range following the surrounding sedimentary cycle. The dominance of fluvial discharge and marine intrusion changes over geologic time in the Kutai Basin is demonstrated through the oscillation curves. Therefore, PCA can quickly analyze large amounts of data, saving time and effort while providing valuable insights into the cyclicity of life mode in the stratigraphic records from ichnofabric.

Keywords: cyclostratigraphy, depositional systems, Kutai Basin, oscillation curves, principal component analysis (PCA), sedimentary cyclicity

1. Introduction

Understanding sedimentary cycles and paleobiological rhythms is crucial for reconstructing ancient environments and geological histories [1, 2]. Traditional methods of analyzing ichnological data need a more advanced approach to quantify the complex interplay between ichnofabric variables and sedimentary processes [3, 4]. PCA offers a potent solution by simplifying intricate data and highlighting significant variables [5]. This study aims to apply PCA to ichnological research, focusing on sedimentary cycles and paleobiological rhythms to offer more precise insights into the interactions between biological activity and sedimentary processes. The ultimate objective is to enhance the accuracy of reconstructions of ancient environments.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1. Geological Setting

The Kutai Basin, positioned at the junction of the Eurasian, Pacific, and Indian-Australian Plates, is flanked by the Kuching High, Mangkalihat Peninsula, Makassar Strait, and Meratus Mountains. This tectonically complex setting heavily influences the basin's geological characteristics. As shown in the geological map by Supriatna et al. [6], outcrops in the basin may belong to the PulauBalang, Balikpapan, and Kampung Baru Formations.

The Kutai Basin's history is marked by its development as an extensional basin filled with Eocene to Oligocene marine deposits, followed by Miocene regressive sediments [7]. The basin's depositional environments are influenced by Miocene tectonics and range from deltaic to deep marine settings [8]. The formation of the Samarinda Anticlinorium, driven by inversion tectonics since the Middle Miocene,

highlights the basin's ongoing evolution, with sedimentation continuing to advance towards the Makassar Strait [9].

2.2. Data

This comprehensive study meticulously analyzed twenty outcrops and their six hundred forty ichnofabric units, which are distributed across the Samarinda Area in the Kutai Basin, East Kalimantan, within the Serravallian-Tortonian sequence (Figure 1). The ichnofabric units, as defined by Arifullah et al. [10], formed the basis for the analysis. Critical data utilized in this study included semi-quantitative variables such as bioturbation index (BI), ichnodiversity (ID), number of behaviours (NB), penetration depth (PD), and burrow diameter (DM), all of which were employed in a PCA. Additionally, lithofacies data from two model outcrops, BER-02 and TAM-02, located along a strike line in the NE direction and separated by approximately 30 km, were used to support the analysis. The study also incorporated secondary data from Arifullah et al. [10], including dominant ichnofossils and the average scores for BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM.

Figure 1. The modified geological map of the Samarinda Area was republished with authorization from the Geological Agency, Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources of Indonesia [6].

2.3. Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

This study was visualized as a multidimensional space, with each dimension representing a different ichnofabric variables [10]. A total of 640 ichnofabric units were analyzed using five variables: BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM. Instead of manually selecting which variables to keep, PCA objectively highlighted the most essential variables while maintaining the overall data structure [5]. Before applying PCA, the data was standardized, with BI, ID, and NB being quantified directly and PD and DM converted into discrete numbers.

The analysis was conducted using PAST-3 software, which reduced the five-dimensional data into principal components (PCs), simplifying visualization. Only PCs with an eigenvalue of one or higher were kept, with PC-1 and PC-2 being the most significant. These components were plotted on a scatter diagram to visualize relationships between variables. Biplot lines in the scatter diagram showed correlations between the PCs and the ichnofabric variables. Additionally, each ichnofabric unit was represented as curve lines in the sedimentary log, displaying trends similar to those seen in wireline logging, and offering further insights into sedimentary processes.

2.4. Lithofacies analysis

A comprehensive lithofacies analysis was conducted to understand the flow regime, examining sedimentary structures, textures, bedding contacts, and geometries. Lithofacies codes, partially adapted from Miall [11], were developed to guide the study. The study also utilized paleocurrent measurements, a valuable source of additional data on regional paleo-sedimentation. This analysis aimed to identify correlations between the flow regime and ichnofabric characteristics, and by transforming these variables into PCs, the study explored potential connections between lithofacies changes and ichnofabric features.

3. Results

3.1. New components

Figure 2 shows the eigenvalues for PC-1 through PC-5, with PC-1 and PC-2 accounting for over 60% of the total variance, making them suitable for further analysis. According to Liu et al. [12], Figure 3 shows that PC-1 is strongly correlated with ichnodiversity (ID, $r = 0.86$) and the number of behaviours (NB, $r = 0.82$) and moderately with the bioturbation index (BI, $r = 0.6$). Meanwhile, PC-2 moderately correlates with penetration depth (PD, $r = 0.72$) and burrow diameter (DM, $r = 0.69$). It suggests that PC-1 primarily represents BI, ID, and NB, while PC-2 represents PD and DM, highlighting more significant variability in the former variables. These relationships are illustrated in a scatter plot (Figure 4).

Figure 2. The display of PC-1's eigenvalues through PC-5. Only PC-1 and PC-2 have values exceeding 1, and their cumulative variance percentage is greater than 60%.

Figure 3. Ichnofabric variables' coefficient correlations (r) with PC-1 and PC-2.

3.2. Scatter diagram

Table 1 illustrates an example of the scores for PC-1 and PC-2 across 640 ichnofabric units, with their distribution visualized in a scatter diagram and biplot lines in Figure 4. The biplot lines indicate the correlation between ichnofabric variables and the principal components, with the angle magnitude showing a stronger correlation between PD and PC-2 than DM and PC-2. The length of the biplot lines reflects the variance, with ID exhibiting a more significant deviation than BI. The scatter pattern reveals no linear relationship between PC-1 and PC-2, with scores aligning more with PC-1, consistent with their eigenvalues. When PC-1 and PC-2 scores are zero, the average values for BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM are 2.49, 1.69, 1.28, 2.28, and 2.18, respectively. Depending on whether the scores are above or below zero, these values must be adjusted accordingly to meet the criteria.

3.3. Sedimentary logs & PC-1 and PC-2 curves

To better understand the outcrops, ichnofabric data were visualized using sedimentary logs, tiering diagrams, and principal component (PC-1 and PC-2) curves. This study focuses on two key outcrops to analyze phase patterns between PC-1 and PC-2. The BER-02 outcrop in northern Samarinda exhibits an "in-phase" pattern, where PC-1 and PC-2 are positively correlated (Figure 5). In contrast, the TAM-02 outcrop in southern Samarinda shows an "out-of-phase" pattern with a negative correlation (Figure 6).

The BER-02 outcrop, predominantly composed of sandstone with shale, is a treasure trove of diverse sedimentary structures and a coarsening/thickening upward sequence. The PC-1 and PC-2 curves in this outcrop reveal repeated 'in-phase' movements, effectively dividing the stratigraphic section into four distinct units.

Table 1. The illustration is an instance of ichnofabric tabulation, presenting various ichnofabric units found in TAM-02 outcrops [13]. Each ichnofabric unit BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM produces PC-1, PC-2, PC-3, PC-4, and PC-5 scores.

IU	BI	ID	NB	PD	DM	PC-1	PC-2	PC-3	PC-4	PC-5
03-Pa-16	3	4	2	6	1.2	2.33	-1.56	-0.27	0.38	-0.71
03-Op-11	2	2	2	20	2	1.08	0.23	0.69	0.97	0.62
03-Pa-17	5	6	2	8	1	4.39	-1.18	-0.33	-0.72	-1.96
03-Ch-04e	2	1	1	18	1	-0.89	0.45	0.46	-0.17	0.09
03-Ma-05	4	4	2	10	2	2.95	-0.31	-0.46	0.26	-0.63
03-Ma-06	4	4	2	12	1.8	2.95	-0.31	-0.46	0.26	-0.63

Figure 4. In the scatter plot, the data points are scattered by the PC-1 and PC-2 axes. This dispersion aligns with the eigenvalues and % CF of PC-1 and PC-2 in Figure 2 [13].

EXPLANATION

Ichnotaxon

- Schaubcylindrichnus
- Ophiomorpha
- Skolithos
- Paleophycus
- Macaronichnus
- Thalassinoides
- Planolites
- Equilibrichnia
- Fugichnia

Lithofacies

- Sr : Ripple cross stratification sandstone
- Sh : Horizontal bedding/laminated sandstone
- Sp : Planar cross stratification sandstone
- Sl : Low angle cross stratification sandstone
- Shc : Hummocky cross stratification sandstone
- Sf : Microfold and/or syn sedimentary fault sandstone
- Mm : Mudstone

- FeOx
- Coal layer

Principal Component-1 (PC-1) ~ BI, ID, NB.
Principal Component-2 (PC-2) ~ PD, DM.

1 Unit that grouped based on PC-1 and PC-2 curve pattern: correlation, frequencies and amplitudes

Figure 5. The "in-phase" pattern ranges between 2080 cm and 2930 cm within the 0-2930 cm interval of the BER-2 outcrop as a model [13].

EXPLANATION

Ichnotaxon

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Lithofacies

- Sr : Ripple cross stratification sandstone
 Sh : Horizontal bedding/laminated sandstone
 Shcs : Hummocky Cross Stratification sandstone
 St : Trough cross stratification sandstone
 Hm : Heterolithic mudstone
 Mm : Mudstone
- FeOx
 Coal layer
- Principal Component-1 (PC-1) – BI, ID, NB.
 Principal Component-2 (PC-2) – PD, DM.

① Unit that grouped based on PC-1 and PC-2 curve pattern: correlation, frequencies and amplitudes

Figure 6. The "out-of-phase" pattern ranges from 1040 cm to 2210 cm in the TAM-2 outcrops within the 0-7510 cm interval as a model [13].

4. Discussion

The passage examines the interaction between biological processes and sedimentary cycles within the framework of cyclostratigraphy, focusing on their role in shaping trace fossils. Byers and Plotnick underscore the importance of tracemakers' activities, such as burrowing and feeding, which are influenced by recurring sedimentary cycles [1, 2]. Nathan et al., Levinton and Reise further highlight how factors like tracemaker size, age, and environmental needs interact with these cyclic processes [14–16]. It is important to note that these processes are driven by natural rhythms such as tides and seasons, which play a crucial role in shaping the environment and its biological interactions.

In cyclostratigraphic terms, the BER-02 outcrop shows in-phase primary and secondary cyclicity (PC-1 and PC-2), indicating a stable environment with regular sedimentation. This synchronization suggests consistent bioturbation patterns typical of deltaic systems, where predictable cyclic processes drive sedimentation [13]. In contrast, the TAM-02 outcrop displays out-of-phase cyclicity, reflecting an environment affected by irregular events like storms or fluctuating salinity. It leads to more chaotic sedimentary cycles and biological interactions, which are characteristic of estuarine settings [13].

Both outcrops belong to the ancient Mahakam Delta system, with BER-02 representing a more stable, active delta region and TAM-02 reflecting the variable conditions of an estuarine environment. These contrasting cyclic patterns within the same system illustrate the dynamic nature of cyclostratigraphy, where phase alignment between biological activity and sedimentary cycles can provide insights into the paleoenvironmental conditions of ancient sedimentary environments.

5. Conclusion

This study applied PCA to ichnofabric data from the Kutai Basin, revealing key patterns in paleobiological rhythms. The analysis identified two principal components, PC-1 and PC-2, which captured significant variance across the data. The contrasting sedimentary patterns in the BER-02 and TAM-02 outcrops highlighted the dynamic nature of cyclostratigraphy within the ancient Mahakam Delta system. The results demonstrate PCA's effectiveness in simplifying complex ichnological data, providing practical insights into the interplay between biological activity and sedimentary processes in ancient environments, which can be applied in future research and field studies.

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